

Varying Valency of Gold with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles.

Part I.

BY

SIR PRAFULLA CHANDRA RAY.

In continuation of the study on the varying valency of platinum (Ray, T., 1923, 123, 133) that of gold has recently been undertaken. In the present communication have been described some bi-, ter-, quadri-, and quinque-valent gold compounds, showing thereby that the valency of gold like that of platinum is variable with respect to mercaptanic radicles.

Bi-, Ter-, and Quadri-valent Gold.

The starting mercaptanic derivative in this case also was diethyldisulphide, which on treatment with gold chloride (chlorauric acid), yielded a crystalline compound having the empirical formula $\text{EtS}\cdot\text{AuCl}_2$, to which may at first sight be assigned the graphic formula,

$\text{EtS}\cdot\text{Au} \begin{matrix} \text{Cl} \\ \text{Cl} \end{matrix}$ the gold behaving as tervalent. This

formula seemed to be unlikely as it would imply that during the reaction, the disulphide had undergone scission, thus: $\text{EtS} \begin{matrix} \vdots \\ \vdots \end{matrix} \text{SEt}$. Moreover, the product of

the corresponding reaction with platinic chloride had the formula $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2\text{PtCl}_2$, which has been shown to be a derivative of quinquevalent platinum and a sulphonium compound as well (*loc. cit.*). It was natural to suppose that the simple formula of the gold compound should be doubled, that is, it should be $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2\cdot 2\text{AuCl}_2$.

Determination of the molecular weight by the freezing point method has justified this conclusion. The compound can thus be represented as

according as the gold is taken to function as bi- or quadri-valent. This constitutional formula of the chloromercaptide brings it into intimate relationship with the numerous sulphonium iodomercaptide derivatives, which the author has been studying during the last ten years (T., 1916, 109, 131, 603; 1917, 111, 101, etc.), where it is shown that the so-called "molecular compounds" of the type $\text{R}_2\text{S}_2 \cdot \text{HgI}_2 \cdot \text{R}'\text{I}$ are in reality "atomic compounds" of the sulphonium type. Diethyldisulphide also furnishes another compound with gold chloride having the empirical formula $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2 \cdot \text{Au}_4\text{Cl}_2$. Its constitution may be represented as

where sulphur is sexavalent and gold alternately bi- and ter-valent. Instances of chain compounds of sexavalent sulphur have already been given (Ray, T., 1919, 115, 548).

Bivalent gold evidently occurs in the compound $\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2$ —the product of the interaction of the monopotassium mercaptide (Ray, T., 1923, 123, 133) and gold chloride. It may be graphically represented as

one atom of gold behaving as bi- and the other as ter-valent.

Benzaldiethylene tetrasulphide (RAY, T., 1924, 125, 1141) on treatment with gold chloride yielded the compound, conforming to the formula

be represented as

the gold functioning alternately as bi- and quadri-valent. When, however, benzaldiethylene trisulphide is similarly treated it has the structure broken up according to the scheme :

diethylene disulphide (1:4-dithian) being the degradation product. Evidently this scission takes place on account of the molecule being loaded with the heavy radicles of gold chloride. It has been shown in the previous communication (*loc. cit.*) that mercuric chloride and even a light radicle like methyl iodide brings about similar rupture. Representing the dithian molecule by A, the following compounds have been obtained : (a) 6A, Au₄Cl₃ ;

(b) $5A, Au_3Cl_3$; (c) $4A, Au_3Cl_4$; (d) $4A, Au_3Cl_2$; (e) $3A, Au_3Cl_2$ and (f) $3A, Au_3Cl_2$. In all these cases the temperature of the reaction varied as a rule from 28° to 55° . In one special case both the component solutions were heated to 78° and the resulting compound had the formula $3(C_2H_4S_2)Au_3Cl_2$ (g), the 1:4-dithian molecule yielding a still simpler degradation product, namely, ethylene disulphide. It might be urged that there is the possibility of some of these compounds being contaminated with traces of reduced gold or of being mixtures. An alcoholic solution of gold chloride has, no doubt, been sometimes found to turn slightly turbid in course of a quarter of an hour or so, but the reactions involved were finished in less than a couple of minutes; moreover, within wide limits of temperature and concentration of the reacting components as also in both alcoholic and ethereal solutions the identical compound, *e.g.*, compound (a) has often been obtained. Hence the chances of their being mixtures are precluded.

The anomalous nature of these chlorides can be easily explained if the atoms of gold be taken as bi- and ter-valent respectively as in the instances cited above. Thus $6A, Au_4Cl_3$ may be represented as

in which only one atom of sulphur of each of the dithian molecules becomes quadrivalent, the sulphur atoms at the extreme ends of the chain taking up the chlorine atoms, thus converting it into a sulphonium compound.

by the interaction of sodium dithioethylene glycol and gold chloride in acetone solution. The corresponding platinum compound has also been isolated. The disodium mercaptide was also treated with an ethereal solution of gold chloride. It was anticipated that the reaction would proceed as follows

but the compound actually obtained had the formula $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_4 \cdot \text{Au}_3\text{Cl}$. The reaction no doubt takes place according to the equation :

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bi-, Ter-, and Quadri-valent Gold.

Action of Gold Chloride on Diethyl Disulphide.—The disulphide was treated with an excess of an aqueous solution of gold chloride and continuously stirred. At first a pasty deep yellow mass was obtained, which on ‘teasing’ with a rod solidified into a crystalline product. It was further purified by recrystallisation from boiling toluene. (Found: Au = 59.90; Cl = 21.39; S = 10.25. $\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}$, requires Au = 59.90; Cl = 21.58; S = 9.73 per cent.). The determination of the molecular weight by the freezing point method (in naphthalene) gave the result as 655, 666.8 and 670.3 respectively, the calculated molecular weight being 658. The compound when dissolved in naphthalene slowly deposits particles of gold; care should therefore be taken to finish the operation within half an hour. The determination of the molecular weight by the ebullioscopic method (in toluene) gave unsatisfactory

results for similar reasons. In fact, the separation of gold in this case is much more rapid. The compound slowly darkens on exposure to light due to separation of fine particles of gold. If, however, the above reaction be not allowed to go beyond the pasty stage and the mass extracted with ether, a portion goes into solution and the ethereal extract on spontaneous evaporation deposits a white amorphous powder, which conforms to the formula $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2, \text{Au}_4\text{Cl}_2$ (Found: $\text{Au}=79.36$; $\text{Cl}=7.45$; $\text{S}=7.76$. Theory requires $\text{Au}=80.33$; $\text{Cl}=7.24$; $\text{S}=6.53$ per cent.). The crystalline insoluble residue was found to be identical with the previous compound.

Action of Gold Chloride on Disodium Dithioethylene Glycol.—To the dimercaptide suspended in ether was added an ethereal solution of gold chloride. Reaction at once commenced and the mixture was heated under reflux for 3-4 hours. A light brown precipitate put in an appearance. It was filtered and washed with water several times and dried in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. (Found: $\text{Au}=59.90$; $\text{S}=25.55$; $\text{Cl}=3.75$. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{S}_8\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}$ requires $\text{Au}=59.42$; $\text{S}=25.74$ and $\text{Cl}=3.57$ per cent.).

Action of Gold Chloride on Monopotassium Dithioethylene Glycol.—In the case of platinum it has already been found that the particular valency which the metal might take up depends upon the concentration as also the temperature of the participants (Ray, T., 1923, 123, 133). Similar *modus operandi* was adopted in this case. 12 c.c. of gold chlorine solution (1 c.c. = 0.0260 gm. Au) were added to 0.5500 gm. of the potassium salt of dithioethylene glycol dissolved in 15 c.c. of water at 5°, 28°, 65° and 80° in different preparations. A brown precipitate was formed in each case. It was washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried in a vacuum. All the preparations were found to be identical in composition. (Found: $\text{Au}=62.23$;

Cl = 4.65; S = 21.18. $C_4H_8S_4Au_3Cl$ requires Au = 62.39; Cl = 5.62 and S = 20.27 per cent.).

Action of Gold Chloride on Benzaldithylene Tetrasulphide.—An alcoholic solution of gold chloride was added in a thin stream under vigorous agitation to an ethereal solution of the sulphide. A flocculent reddish precipitate was formed. It was washed with ether and dried in a vacuum. It had the formula $2[C_6H_5CHS_4(C_2H_4)_2]$, Au_3Cl_4 , $(C_2H_5)_2O$.* (Found: Au = 42.40; Cl = 10.53; S = 19.70. $C_{28}H_{38}OS_8Au_3Cl_4$ requires Au = 43.62; Cl = 10.48; S = 18.89 per cent.). The same compound was also obtained when both the components were mixed in ethereal solution. From the filtrate of the latter again a further quantity of a precipitate with identical composition was obtained.

Action of Gold Chloride on Benzaldithylene Trisulphide.—(α) *Expt. 1.*—0.1940 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 5 c.c. of alcohol. To it was added 2 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c. = 0.0510 gm. Au). The reaction was carried out at 55°. *Expt. 2.*—The same quantity of the sulphide was dissolved in 10 c.c. of alcohol and to it was added 3 c.c. of gold chloride of the same strength as above. The temperature of the reaction was 40°. *Expt. 3.*—The same quantity of the trisulphide was this time dissolved in 15 c.c. of alcohol, and to it was added 3 c.c. of gold chloride. The temperature of the reaction was 30°. *Expt. 4.*—0.1730 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 4 c.c. of alcohol and to it was added 8 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c. = 0.0155 gm.

* In these and the compounds of gold and platinum to be subsequently described a molecule or more of ether or alcohol of combination, as the case may be, often occurs. (Compare Rây, T., 1924, 125, 1143). The filtrate from the product of reaction of benzaldithylene trisulphide and platinum chloride (*loc. cit.*) in alcohol deposited a compound of the formula $C_{11}H_{14}S_3PtCl_3 \cdot 3EtOH$. (Found: Pt = 30.45; Cl = 9.95; C = 31.26; H = 4.73. Theory requires Pt = 30.40; Cl = 10.96; C = 31.48; H = 4.93 per cent.).

Au) at 28°. *Expt. 5.*—0.2160 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 5 c.c. of alcohol and to it was added 10 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c.=0.0155 gm. Au). The temperature of the reaction was 50°. In each of these cases the compounds obtained had identical composition. The formation of one and the same compound within wide limits of temperature and concentration also precludes the possibility of their being any mixtures. It conformed to the formula $6[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_4Cl_3$. (Found: Au=49.06; Cl=6.78; S=23.52. $C_{24}H_{48}S_{12}, Au_4Cl_3$ requires Au=48.79; Cl=6.79; S=23.77 per cent.).

(b) 0.2474 gm. of the trisulphide was dissolved in 5 c.c. of ether and cooled with ice-water. To it was added an excess of gold chloride in ether (1 c.c.=0.0273 gm. Au) under vigorous agitation. The brown precipitate was washed with ether and dried in a vacuum. It conformed to the formula $5[(C_2H_4)_2S_3], Au_3Cl_5, 1\frac{1}{2}(C_2H_5)_2O$. (Found: Au=42.00; Cl=12.18. Theory requires Au=42.03; Cl=12.62 per cent.).

(c) In this experiment the components were dissolved in ethereal solution and were mixed in indefinite proportions. The compound had the formula $4[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_3Cl_4, \frac{1}{2}(C_2H_5)_2O$. (Found: Au=47.61; Cl=11.42. Theory requires Au=47.38; Cl=11.36 per cent.).

(d) 0.1300 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 3 c.c. of alcohol and heated to about 72°. To it was added 10 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c.=0.0155 gm. Au). The compound obtained had the formula $4[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_3Cl_2$. (Found: Au=52.17; Cl=6.35; S=22.43. Theory requires Au=51.75; Cl=6.22 and S=22.41 per cent.).

(e) 0.4991 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in alcohol. To it was added drop by drop under constant agitation 1 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c.=0.0623 gm. Au). A purple precipitate was obtained. It

was washed first with benzene and then with alcohol and dried in a vacuum. Under the microscope it revealed a brown, spongy texture but no gold particles. It conformed to the formula $3[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_3Cl_3, C_2H_5OH$. (Found: Au=55.76; Cl=6.98. Theory requires Au=55.34; Cl=6.65 per cent.).

(f) (*Expt. 1*).—0.3582 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 25 c.c. of alcohol and heated on the waterbath to 60°. To it was added an excess of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c.=0.1066 gm Au) all at once and agitated on the waterbath between 60-70°. (*Expt. 2*).—0.2750 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 10 c.c. of alcohol and heated to 40-50°. To it was added 6.5 c.c. of an alcoholic solution of gold chloride (1 c.c.=0.0425 gm. Au) all at once and vigorously agitated. In both these preparations the compounds had identical composition and conformed to the formula $3[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_2Cl_2, C_2H_5OH$. (Found: Au=45.61, 45.64; Cl=8.43, 8.74; S=23.22, 23.80. Theory requires Au=45.24; Cl=8.15; S=22.04 per cent.).

(g) 0.4110 gm. of the sulphide was dissolved in 30 c.c. of alcohol and heated on the waterbath and to it was added 6.5 c.c. of gold chloride in alcohol (1 c.c.=0.0425 gm. Au) and again heated on the waterbath for a few minutes more. The product agreed with the formula $3[(C_2H_4)_2S_2], Au_3Cl_3, C_2H_5OH$. (Found: Au=60.34; Cl=7.27; S=19.08. Theory requires Au=60.06; Cl=7.22; and S=19.51 per cent.).

Quinquevalent Gold.

Disodium Dithioethylene Glycol.—To an ethereal solution of dithioethylene glycol, very finely divided metallic sodium was added, care being taken to exclude moisture. Slow evolution of hydrogen took place and a fine

crystalline powder of the dimercaptide was formed. (Found: Na=32·71. $C_2H_4S_2Na_2$ requires Na=33·34 per cent.).

Action of Gold Chloride on Disodium Dithioethylene glycol.—The dimercaptide was suspended in acetone and an acetone solution of gold chloride was added. The mixture was digested on the water bath for about an hour. The product had the formula $C_{10}H_{20}S_{10}Au_2$. (Found: Au=47·38, S=36·19,* C=14·05. Theory requires Au=46·13, S=37·50, C=14·00 per cent.).

Action of Gold Chloride on Triethylene Trisulphide.—Alcoholic solutions of the components were mixed together. An orange-colored precipitate was immediately formed. It conformed to the formula $(C_2H_4S)_3 \cdot 2AuCl_3$. (Found: Au=50·90; Cl=26·39; S=11·03. $C_6H_{12}S_3Au_2Cl_6$ requires Au=50·06; Cl=27·06; S=12·20 per cent.). The alcoholic filtrate containing an excess of gold chloride deposited on spontaneous evaporation, a crop of white crystals of the formula $(C_2H_4S)_3 \cdot AuCl_2$. (Found: Au=44·00; Cl=15·27; S=20·73. $C_6H_{12}S_3AuCl_2$ requires Au=43·97; Cl=15·87; S=21·43 per cent.).

In conclusion, I avail myself of this opportunity to express my cordial thanks to Messrs. Indu Bhusan Sen Gupta and Khitish Chandra Rây for the patience and skill with which they conducted the experimental part of this investigation.

COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
UNIVERSITY OF CALCUTTA.

[Received May 29, 24]

* The estimation was effected by fusion with Na_2CO_3 and KNO_3 . Traces of sulphur are converted into sulphonic acids owing to the presence of the radicle C_2H_4 , and hence the percentage of sulphur comes out slightly low. (Compare Rây, T., 1920, 117, 1091).

